

Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XXXVII. ONNO and ONON Donor Chelating Bis-bidentate Azo Dye Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury(II)

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Two bis-bidentate chelating azo dye ligands, 1-(2'-hydroxynaphthyl)azo-2-hydroxynaphthyl-4-sulphonic acid and 1-(8'-hydroxyquinolyl-5')azo-2-hydroxynaphthyl-4-sulphonic acid having ONNO and ONON donor atoms have been prepared. Both these ligands form octahedral and distorted octahedral complexes with bivalent Co, Ni and Cu ions and tetrahedral complexes with bivalent Zn, Cd and Hg ions. All the complexes are polymeric in nature. The characterisation of the ligands and the complexes is made on the basis of analytical, conductance magnetic ir, electronic spectra and esr spectral data.

The azo dyes are well-known for their strong pharmacological activities¹, in addition to their immense analytical applications². The present paper describes the preparation and characterisation of two azodyes and their metal complexes with bivalent Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Hg ions.

Results and Discussion

All the metal complexes (Table 1) have the compositions $[M_2L_2 \cdot 4H_2O]$, $[M'_2L_2]$, $[ML' \cdot 2H_2O]_n$ and $[M'L']_n$, where $M = Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} ; $M' = Zn^{II}$, Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} ; $LH_2 = 1-(2'-hydroxynaphthyl)azo-2-hydroxynaphthyl-4-sulphonic$ acid; $L'H_2 = 1-(8'-hydroxyquinolyl-5')azo-2-hydroxynaphthyl-4-sulphonic$ acid. The complexes are quite stable at room temperature. They are amorphous in nature having high melting points and insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in dioxane and DMF. Non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is indicated from their low Δ_M values (5.2–6.8 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$).

In the ir spectra of the ligands, the bands at $\sim 3400 cm^{-1}$ (OH) was lowered due to intramolecular O–H...N hydrogen bonding. The absence of these bands in the metal complexes indicates the deprotonation of phenolic OH groups, thereby showing the bonding of the oxygen atom to the metal atom. The bands at 1580 (LH_2) and 1560 cm^{-1} ($L'H_2$) can be ascribed to $\nu_{N=N}$ vibration. In the metal complexes with LH_2 the band at $\sim 1390 cm^{-1}$ and with $L'H_2$ at $\sim 1540 cm^{-1}$ indicate the coordination of both the azo nitrogen atoms of the former ligand to the metal ions and one of the azo nitrogen atoms of the latter ligand to the metal ion³. The band at 1520 cm^{-1} (C–O) suffered

bathochromic shift of 10–15 cm^{-1} in the metal chelates indicating bonding of the phenolic oxygen atoms to the metal atom⁴. In case of the complexes with $L'H_2$ the band appearing at $\sim 1340 cm^{-1}$ may be ascribed to C=N band of the oxinate group. In the free ligand, this band occurred at $\sim 1435 cm^{-1}$ and this shifting to lower frequency region in the complexes indicates considerably lower double bond character of the C=N band due to involvement of ring nitrogen to the metal atom. A sharp band at $\sim 1100 cm^{-1}$ in this ligand attributed to C–O of the oxine moiety and its decrease to $\sim 1090 cm^{-1}$ in the chelates suggests the coordination of this oxygen atom to the metal atoms⁶. In case of all the complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} , the presence of coordinated water molecule is shown by the appearance of a broad band at ~ 3450 and sharp bands at ~ 1450 and $\sim 840 cm^{-1}$ attributed to OH stretching, bending and rocking vibrations respectively⁶. The evidence of bonding of oxygen and nitrogen atoms to the metal ions is tentatively assigned by the appearance of bands at about 500 (M–O) and 400 cm^{-1} (M–N)⁷.

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} complexes showed bands at ~ 9150 , ~ 18540 , ~ 21775 and $\sim 33250 cm^{-1}$ assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and CT transitions respectively. The spectral parameters like Dq (939, 937) cm^{-1} , B (877, 6834) cm^{-1} , β_{2g} (0.90, 0.85), ν_2/ν_1 (2.06, 2.03) and σ (11.11, 17.6) suggest an octahedral structure for the Co^{II} complexes. The Ni^{II} complexes exhibit four bands at ~ 11250 , ~ 16460 , ~ 24645 and $\sim 31300 cm^{-1}$ attributed to the ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_1(P)$ and CT transitions respectively. These complexes are suggested to be octahedral based upon their band positions, magnetic moments and spectral parameter values, Dq (1070, 1095) cm^{-1} ,

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B M	Mol. wt.
		M	N		
LH ₂	Brown	—	6.80 (7.10)	—	368
LH ₂	Reddish brown	—	9.70 (10.63)	—	372
[Co ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Brown	11.80 (12.10)	5.20 (5.70)	2.45	874
[Cu ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Green	12.30 (12.91)	5.40 (5.69)	1.30	882
[Ni ₂ L ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Green	11.70 (12.06)	5.30 (5.75)	2.70	896
[Zn ₂ L ₂]	Black	13.50 (14.29)	5.70 (6.12)	—	835
[Cd ₂ L ₂]	Green	21.80 (22.28)	5.10 (5.55)	—	915
[Hg ₂ L ₂]	Brown	33.10 (33.84)	4.20 (4.72)	—	1050
[CoL'(H ₂ O) ₅] _n	Brown	11.60 (12.07)	5.20 (5.73)	5.10	455
[NiL'(H ₂ O) ₅] _n	Brown	11.70 (12.03)	5.10 (5.74)	3.30	562
[CuL'(H ₂ O) ₅] _n	Green	12.10 (12.90)	5.20 (5.68)	1.90	435
[ZnL'] _n	Light brown	13.70 (14.28)	5.80 (6.10)	—	412
[CdL'] _n	Blue	21.60 (22.23)	5.20 (5.54)	—	460
[HgL'] _n	Brown	32.50 (33.79)	4.20 (4.71)	—	542

B (657, 679.6) cm^{-1} , β_{35} (0.63, 0.65), ν_2/ν_1 (1.53, 1.54) and σ (58.7, 53.8), which are in agreement with those reported in the literature. The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes showed broad bands at ~ 14750 and ~ 28350 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ and CT transitions respectively, indicating the presence of distorted octahedral stereochemistry around the metal ions⁸.

The lower μ_{eff} values of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with ligand (LH₂) were found to be 2.45, 2.70 and 1.30 B.M. respectively. Sub-normal magnetic moments of these complexes can be ascribed to partial quenching of paramagnetism due to metal-metal interaction in a dimeric structure⁹. The metal complexes formed by the above metal ions with the ligand (L'H₂) exhibited the normal magnetic moments of octahedral complexes. The Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are presumably dimeric tetrahedral with LH₂ and polymeric tetrahedral with L'H₂, suggested on the basis of analytical, conductance, solubility tests, high melting points, spectral and molecular weight data.

The g -values of complexes [Cu₂L₂(H₂O)₄] are $g_1 = g_2 = 2.033$ and $g_3 = 2.207$. From the esr spectrum, it is evident that the symmetry around Cu^{II} is axial (two values tensor), i.e. the symmetry is tetragonal. The ground state of the complex is $d_{x^2-y^2}$. The axial symmetry parameter G -value (6.27) indicates strong exchange interaction among the magnetically inequivalent Cu^{II} ions in the unit cell¹⁰. The g -values (< 2.3) indicate mixed Cu-N and Cu-O bonds¹¹.

Hence both the azo dyes act as doubly-bidentate ligands bonded through phenolic oxygens, azo

nitrogens and oxine nitrogen and oxygen atoms. The most probable structures of the complexes with the ligands LH₂ and L'H₂ can be represented by the Figs. 1 and 2 respectively.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Experimental

All the chemicals were of B.D.H. or E. Merck grade. Both the azo dyes were synthesised by the usual method: LH₂, m.p. 280° (Found: C, 58.2; H, 3.1; N, 6.8; S, 7.5. C₂₀H₁₄O₅N₂S calcd. for: C, 60.91; H, 3.55; N, 7.10; S, 8.13%); L'H₂, m.p. > 250°d (Found: C, 56.5; H, 2.9; N, 9.7; S, 7.4. C₁₉H₁₃O₅N₃S calcd. for: C, 57.72; H, 3.29; N, 10.63; S, 8.11%).

The metal complexes were prepared by adding ethanolic solution of the metal chlorides to the ligands in dioxane in 1:1 ratio and maintaining pH of the resulting solution to 7, where the metal chelates separated out. The compounds were filtered, washed with ethanol, dioxane and by ether and then dried under reduced pressure.

The metal and nitrogen contents were estimated by standard methods. The conductance was measured in DMF solution (10⁻³ M). The magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature by Gouy method. Molecular weight was determined

at room temperature by Rast method using camphor as the solvent. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (10^{-2} M DMF) on a Hilger-Watt uvispeck spectrophotometer and esr spectra on a Varian E-4 instrument.

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